

EFFECTS OF COOLING RATE ON THE MECHANICAL AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF SELF-REINFORCED POLYETHYLENE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Self-reinforced polyethylene (PE) composites offer advantages of interfacial compatibility, enhanced mechanical performance, and full recyclability potential due to their homopolymer composition. This study investigates the effect of cooling rate during composite fabrication on the mechanical and thermal properties of self-reinforced PE composites consisting of ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fabric and high-density polyethylene (HDPE) matrix. Composite sheets with 50 wt.% fabric content were manufactured using powder impregnation and hot compaction techniques, with cooling rates varied from 0.76 to 424.92 °C/min through controlled air cooling, cold metal block transfer, and ice immersion methods. The uniaxial quasi-static tensile testing revealed bilinear stress-strain behavior, presumably attributed to yarn de-crimping followed by the elastic behavior of the composite, with modulus values ranging from 2.2 to 3.8 GPa in the initial region and higher values (8.1 to 11.3 GPa) in the elastic region. Mechanical properties showed minimal dependence on cooling rate. Thermal analysis revealed that the melting temperature (T_m) of HDPE decreased from ~130 °C to ~126.5 °C with increasing cooling rate, following a linear correlation with logarithmic cooling rate. The total degree of crystallinity of the PE composites (i.e., the sum of crystallinity of HDPE matrix and UHMWPE fabric) decreased from ~85% to ~75% with increasing cooling rate, approaching the theoretical mixing rule value of 72.4%. These findings suggest that self-reinforced PE composites exhibit relative insensitivity to cooling rate variations in the range of 0.76 to 424.92 °C/min, which may be attributed to low interfacial strength between PE matrix and PE fabric compared to conventional fiber-reinforced composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Self-reinforced thermoplastic composites are materials in which both the matrix and the reinforcing phase consist of the same polymer, with the benefits of interfacial compatibility, enhanced mechanical performance, and the potential for full recyclability and re-processing [1–3]. The self-reinforced polyethylene (PE) composites are also known for its lightweight, low energy cost during manufacturing, waterproof and high durability. These composites are typically manufactured by consolidating highly oriented PE fibers or films into a bulk matrix, utilizing the high crystallinity and molecular alignment of the reinforcement to achieve significantly higher tensile strength and stiffness than the isotropic PE [2,4]. During composite manufacturing, the control of thermal history is critical to maintain fiber orientation and ensuring optimal interfacial bonding between the fiber and the matrix [3,5]. It has been reported that polyether ether ketone (PEEK) matrix as a semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymer exhibited a transition from brittle to ductile performance as the cooling rate became faster [6,7]. Whether such a transition could be observed for other semi-crystalline polymer composites such as the self-reinforced PE composites is unknown. In this work, we present the

preliminary studies on the mechanical and thermal properties of self-reinforced PE composites affected by the cooling rates during manufacturing.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Powder Impregnation

PE composite sheets were fabricated from ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) fabric (Avient Corporation) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE) powder (Microthene FA70000, LyondellBasell), with 50 wt.% of fabrics, by powder impregnation and compression molding techniques. The UHMWPE fabrics and HDPE powders were used as received.

Two 6" × 4" (152.4 mm × 101.6 mm) pieces were cut from the plain weave UHMWPE fabric, with the cutting direction aligned parallel to the warp and weft fiber directions. The HDPE powder was poured into a 250-micron sieve and sprayed onto the mold by manually vibrating the sieve above the mold. Figure 1(a) shows the top layer of HDPE powder distributed on a piece of UHMWPE fabric. A total of three layers of powder and two layers of fabric were alternately laid up in a mold, as shown in Figure 1(b).

Figure 1. (a) The HDPE powder deposits on the top of, in between, and at the bottom of two UHMWPE fabrics in a mold. (b) Layup of UHMWPE fabric and HDPE powder layers in the mold.

2.2 Compression Molding with Different Cooling Rates

The mold was transferred to a hot press (Carver) pre-heated to 140 °C, and held at 1100 lbs (approximately 45.8 psi or 0.3 MPa) for 15 min on the compression molder before cooling down in place. The processing parameters were optimized in a previous study [8]. A typical temperature profile during compression molding is shown in Figure 2, where the temperature inside the mold were in between 135 °C and 140 °C for more than 10 min. The temperature range was chosen to completely melt the HDPE powder but keep the fabric intact. The compression molder was equipped with an air-cooling accessory. By adjusting the cooling air pressure, cooling rates ranging from 0.76 °C/min to 3.61 °C/min were obtained.

Figure 2. Temperature readings of three thermocouples placed at three different locations inside the mold, in between the composite and mold lid.

Higher cooling rates (above 50 °C/min) were achieved by transferring the mold onto cold metal blocks (Figure 3a) and into an ice bucket (Figure 3b). A second batch using the ice-immersion method was performed to achieve an even higher cooling rate up to 424.92 °C/min. The cooling rates were calculated from the initial cooling periods (e.g., above 100 °C), as listed in Table 1.

Figure 3. (a) Cooling down the mold with composite sample in between two empty metal molds initially at 25 °C. (b) A mold immersed in a bucket of ice. The grey dashed line indicates the location of the mold.

Table 1. Cooling rate at the initial cooling period using different cooling methods.

Cooling Method	Cooling Rate (°C/min)
Adjusting cooling air pressures on the compression molder	0.76
	0.80
	1.18
	3.61
Cold metal blocks	62.48
Ice immersion	167.27
	424.92

2.3 Tensile Testing

From each composite sheet, five rectangular specimens of 0.5" × 5" (12.7 mm × 127 mm) were cut along the principal fiber orientations (0°/90°). Uniaxial quasi-static tensile tests were performed at room temperature on an Instron 5582 test frame at a controlled displacement rate of 2 mm/min. The crosshead movement direction was aligned with the yarn axis. A gauge section of 2.6" (66 mm) long and full width was pre-speckled and monitored by the digital image correlation (DIC, Correlated Solutions) cameras for strain calculation.

2.4 Thermal Analysis

Melting and crystallization behaviors of as-purchased UHMWPE fabric, HDPE powder, and the composite specimens were characterized on the Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC, TA Instruments Q2000) in cyclic temperature ramps between 0 and 200 °C. The heating and cooling rates were 10 °C/min. The tests were performed under N₂ gas flow of 50 mL/min.

The melting point (T_m) was determined as the temperature corresponding to peak maxima of the melting peaks in the first heating cycle. The enthalpy (ΔH) was calculated as the trapezoidal area under the heat capacity curve, as shown in Figure 4. The baseline for peak area calculation was chosen to be the line connecting the 60 °C and 180 °C points. These two points were chosen as they were located on the flat portion of the heat capacity curve at each side of the peak. Degree of crystallinity (χ) was calculated as a ratio of heat of fusion (ΔH_f) measured on the endothermic peaks (during heat cycles) to the heat of fusion of 100% crystallized PE ($\Delta H_f^0 = 293 \text{ J/g}$ [9]).

Figure 4. Heat capacity in three cycles of DSC test for a self-reinforced PE composite: c1 – initial heating from 40 to 200 °C, c2 – cooling cycle from 200 to 0 °C, c3 – re-heating from 0 to 200 °C. The shaded area represents enthalpy (ΔH). The dashed line represents the baseline for area calculation.

2.5 Microscopic Imaging

The cross-section of square samples of 0.5" × 0.5" (12.7 mm × 12.7 mm) cut from composite sheets were imaged on an Olympus DSX1000 microscope. Prior to imaging, the cross-section was first grinded using sandpapers of 180 grit, 600 grit and 1200 grit, and then polished with two pads each soaked with 3 μm and 0.5 μm polishing solution. In between the grinding and polishing steps, the surface was cleaned with soap and water, rinsed with ethanol and dried using compressed air.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Tensile Properties

Tensile properties along the longitudinal direction were obtained by uniaxial tension test. The actual strain rate as calculated from DIC strain was approximately 3×10^{-4} /s. Representative stress-strain curves are shown in Figure 5 for composites obtained at different cooling rates.

Figure 5. Engineering stress vs. engineering strain for PE composites under uniaxial tension. The strain was obtained by DIC. One curve out of five replicates was plotted for composites made at the same cooling rate.

All curves in Figure 5 showed a bilinear behavior, with the slope becoming steeper at around 2 – 3% strain. Opposite to the typical stress-strain behavior of polymers, the transition at around 2 – 3% strain was not a yield point but the onset of a hardening region. For a single yarn detached from woven fabric, a small toe region within 1% strain was associated with fiber de-crimping, i.e., straightening and realigning of the yarn, where the stress almost did not increase and the modulus was near-zero [10,11]. It was assumed that the initial linear region (below 2 – 3 % strain and 100 MPa) observed for PE composites in Figure 5 was a result of de-crimping of yarns in the specimen. The modulus of the initial linear region ranged from 2.2 to 3.8 GPa, much higher than the modulus of pure HDPE (0.8 GPa), suggesting that a portion of yarns had contributed to the stiffness of the composite while other yarns were not fully straightened. The second linear region (beyond 3% strain) corresponds to the elastic behavior of the composites. The modulus of the composite was calculated from the second linear region.

The modulus, tensile strength and ultimate elongation were plotted as a function of cooling rate as shown in Figure 6. The mechanical properties did not show a significant dependence on the cooling rate. The largest differences were observed when the cooling rate increased from 3.61 °C/min to 62.48 °C/min, where the average strength and modulus increased by 57.74 MPa (16%) and 3.15 GPa (39%) respectively. The strength and modulus slightly decreased with cooling rates above 62.48 °C/min. Several factors may explain why mechanical properties remain unaffected by cooling rate: (1) the crystal morphology and crystal size of self-reinforced PE composites were not affected by cooling

rates in the investigated range, though effects might become apparent at lower cooling rates; (2) the interfacial strength between PE matrix and PE fabric (0.5 – 2 MPa) was low, compared to carbon fiber(CF)/epoxy matrix (60 – 100 MPa) or CF/PEEK (30 – 50 MPa).

Figure 6. Tensile strength and modulus of the UHMWPE/HDPE composites as a function of cooling rate.

3.2 Microscopic Morphology

Figure 7(a) showed the micrographs of the as-received fabric, confirming a plain weave architecture. Warp yarns can be clearly observed from the cross-sectional images of the PE composites, as exemplified in Figure 7(b). The presence of crimped yarns supports the hypothesis that yarn de-crimpling was associated with the low-stiffness initial linear region on the stress-strain curve.

Figure 7. Microscopic images of (a) UHMWPE woven fabric as received, (b) cross-section of the self-reinforced PE composite cooled down at 167.27 °C/min.

3.3 Thermal Properties

It is well-established that thermal properties of semi-crystalline polymers are affected by cooling rates [12,13]. From the DSC signals as exemplified in Figure 4, the HDPE matrix and UHMWPE fabric in the PE composite showed separate endothermic peaks in the initial heating cycle, but these peaks collapsed into one peak with a shoulder in the re-heating cycle, since the effects of processing histories specifically the cooling rates on thermal properties of composites were erased by annealing the samples at 200 °C, i.e., the PE crystals had melted and re-crystallized. Therefore, thermal properties, including the T_m of HDPE and χ of the composites, were determined from the first heating cycle.

The heat capacity signals in the first heating cycle were plotted in Figure 8 for one representative sample of the three replicates of the PE composites made at the same cooling rate. Two melting peaks were visible: the melting of HDPE located between 126 °C to 130 °C, and the melting of UHMWPE located above 140 °C. The UHMWPE peak was a convolution of multiple split peaks, which is a signature for highly-oriented UHMWPE fibers with draw ratios typically above 50. The split peaks correspond to transitions of different crystal phases, such as transition from orthorhombic into hexagonal crystals [14].

Figure 8. Heat capacity during the initial heating ramp of PE composites manufactured with difference cooling rates, and the as-received HDPE powder and UHMWPE fabric samples. One out of three replicates were plotted. The curves were vertically shifted for clarity.

As shown in Figure 8, the melting peaks of UHMWPE in the composite were not affected by cooling rate, which was expected considering that the manufacturing temperature of the composites (140 °C) was below the melt temperature of highly oriented UHMWPE crystals. However, T_m of HDPE shifted from ~130 °C to ~126.5 °C as the cooling rate increased, approaching the T_m of as-received HDPE powder. The qualitative trend was within expectation as higher cooling rates promoted formation of imperfect crystals with a lower T_m . The decrease in the T_m of HDPE was most significant when the cooling rate was slow (below 62.48 °C/min). Phenomenologically, T_m of HDPE showed a linear correlation with the log of cooling rate, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. T_m of HDPE and the total degree of crystallinity (χ) of the UHMWPE and HDPE portions in the self-reinforced PE composites, as a function of cooling rate. The green dashed line represents the T_m of as-received HDPE powder. The orange dashed line represents the theoretical χ of composites based on the mixing rule. The dotted orange line represents the χ of as-received UHMWPE fabric.

Crystallinity of the composite (χ) was calculated based on the area under the heat capacity curve, as demonstrated in Figure 4. The χ decreased with cooling rate from $\sim 85\%$ to $\sim 75\%$, as shown in Figure 9, approaching the average crystallinity based on the mixing rule (72.4%) for a composite consisting of 50 wt.% fabric and 50 wt.% matrix. The χ decreased most rapidly in two regions: (1) when cooling rates were below 1.2 °C/min, and (2) from 62.48 to 167.27 °C/min. In both regions the modulus of the composite showed a slight decrease, as shown in Figure 6.

4 SUMMARIES

In summary, self-reinforced PE composites were manufactured from UHMWPE fabric and HDPE matrix by powder impregnation and compression molding. The cooling rates were varied from 0.76 °C/min to 424.92 °C/min. The mechanical and thermal properties of UHMWPE/HDPE composites were not significantly affected by cooling rates. The melt temperature of HDPE matrix decreased with cooling rates and linearly correlated with the logarithmic cooling rates. The total degree of crystallinity of the composites decreased with cooling rates especially in the ranges of 0.76 – 1.18 °C/min and 62.48 – 167.27 °C/min, where the modulus also decreased slightly.

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